

THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DISCHARGE OF BIOPHYSICS

Abstract: this article provides information on the methods of using modern technologies in the streaming of Biophysics.

Keywords: PHET, Circuit Construction, Kit simulation, Crocodile Physics, Yenka, Waves, Optics.

Physics is said to be difficult subject. Physics learning is not an easy task. There is strong evidence all over the world that physics students are not learning the concepts necessary for a good understanding of the physics world. Their learning of scientific facts remains in the classroom only. The computer is one of the most brilliant gifts of science having characteristics of speed, accuracy, reliability and integrity. It can execute over a million instructions per second without any mistake. It can carry our calculation in just a few minutes that would require month If carried out manually. The computational techniques have provided a friend and servant to science, technology and industry. In the present learning process computers are being used for enhancing physics learning also. They can be used to analyze and visualize data, communicate results, run experiment and monitor equipment. Computing can play an important and varied role in advancing physics learning. We point out role of computational techniques namely Simulations, Multimedia, Virtual Reality, Telematics and computer based labs which may deal with those difficulties and increase the learning process. Some good computer programs for learning physics exist. Emergent computational tools and new development in learning theories have contributed to change in education. But we are still in the middle of change process. The main objective of this paper is to discuss role of computer to understand physics and strengthen science and technology.

PHET is a suite of research-based interactive computer simulations for teaching and learning physics, chemistry, math, and other sciences. PHET simulations can be run online or downloaded for free from the PHET website. The simulations are animated, interactive, and game-like environments where students learn through exploration. They emphasize the connections between real-life phenomena and the underlying science, and help make the visual and conceptual models of expert scientists accessible to students. PHET simulations are primarily developed for and tested with university and high school students, but have been found to be educational and fun for students "from grade school to grad school."

The Circuit Construction Kit simulation allows students to build circuits out of virtual batteries, wires, bulbs, resistors, switches, and (in the AC version) capacitors and inductors. The simulation can be used to replace or supplement experiments with real equipment in lecture demos, labs, and tutorials. Some advantages over real equipment are that the simulation allows students to see a visual model for current flow (virtual electrons flow through the wire), the equipment never breaks or wears out, and students can play around without fear of breaking things. Other simulations that can replace real equipment include Faraday's Electromagnetic Lab, Pendulum Lab, Geometric Optics, Masses and Springs, Wave Interference, Wave on a String, and Photoelectric Effect.

Crocodile Physics is a powerful but easy-to-use simulator that lets you model a range of models in electricity, motion and forces, optics and waves. Simply drag parts from the toolbars at the side of the screen, and move or position them as you wish; they start simulating straight away. Click on them to edit settings, and plot graphs to analyse data from your experiment.

Yenka is a suite of educational software products which allows students to simulate scientific experiments, create mathematical models, design electronic circuits or learn computer programming. Yenka is developed by Crocodile Clips Ltd. The software is based around a variety of subjects such as computer programming and chemistry

Yenka uses a unified interface to model reactions in scientific and technological subject areas, often in 3D. The software is intended to display results in real time or simulated time at 0.1x or 10x speed, replicating actual results (for example, a completed circuit will illuminate a light-emitting diode (LED), but applying too much electric current will destroy it). Yenka also allows educators to design lessons and interactive content for students.

Waves

Yenka lets you take a top-down view of wave propagation, and study key phenomena – such as refraction, interference, diffraction and reflection – with water, sound or EM waves.

Point or plane wave sources, and a moving source whose velocity and bearing you can control, generate waves. You can also control the frequency, phase and amplitude of each source.

Add obstacles, reflectors and slits to investigate reflection, refraction, diffraction and interference. Position these components wherever you want, and control properties like size, orientation, damping, slit spacing and width, and the material from which each is made.

Optics

Yenka lets you simulate with a range of components including lenses, prisms, mirrors and light sources, and lets you model ray diagrams.

You can import your own images and investigate how they look when viewed in lenses in mirrors. As shown below, intensity and blurring are modelled.

The rays from the object are drawn as you simulate, letting you trace their path through the optical system.

Properties for all of the optical components can be changed, either by dragging with the mouse or by typing in new values. You can also position the components however you like – a true virtual workbench.

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